

AUTOMATICALLY PROCESSED BIOINSPIRED HIERACHICAL CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES

Verónica Rodríguez-García^{1,2}, Vanesa Martínez³, Daniel Berlanga^{3,4}, Carlos D. González^{2,3} and Roberto Guzmán de Villoria¹

¹ FIDAMC, Foundation for the Research, Development and Application of Composite Materials, Avda. Rita Levi Montalcini 29, 28906 Getafe, Madrid, Spain

² Departamento de Ciencia de los Materiales, ETSI Caminos, Canales y Puertos, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid C/ Profesor Aranguren s/n, 28040 Madrid, Spain

³ IMDEA Materials Institute, C/Eric Kandel, 2, 28906 Getafe, Madrid, Spain

⁴ Departamento de Materiales y Producción Aeroespacial, E.T.S.I. Aeronáutica y del Espacio, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Pza. de Cardenal Cisneros 3, 28040 Madrid, Spain

Keywords: Automatic Tape Lay-up, Bioinspired, Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRP), Laminates

ABSTRACT

One of the main drawbacks of carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRPs) is the delamination and catastrophic failure mechanism they present when reaching their mechanical limits. A way of limiting this kind of failure is investigated in this project. Through an automatic production, bio-inspired CFRP laminates are manufactured. The toughness of the nacre-like laminates presents an increment in comparison to conventional CFRP unidirectional laminates made of the same material.

1 INTRODUCTION

The aerospace industry is demanding a next generation of materials and structures which should overcome some of the current limitations of the carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites (CFRPs). A particularly focus of interest is the internal damage that CFRPs are prone to develop. Since damage is difficult to detect and compromises the structural stability, design of components has to be made considering the presence of defects in CFRPs.

When subjected to certain loads, internal damage in CFRPs is associated to matrix crack and delamination which, at the same time, are related to catastrophic failure. In order to soften the failure mechanisms of crack propagation and delamination, researchers have been studying and looking for enhancing the interlaminar properties of conventional CFRPs with a variety of approaches in the last decade. Some methodologies to improve interlaminar properties are based on adding nanoparticles or nanofillers into the resin, aligning nanotubes in the ply interfaces, on fiber surface treatment or sizing or on z-pinning/stitching [1]. Although successful outcomes have been obtained, these strategies involve difficulties when talking about scaling them into industrial manufacturing processes for making large CFRPs laminates or components.

This study proposes a design of new systems capable of softening the catastrophic failure of CFRPs laminates using manufacturing methodologies currently implemented in the industry.

2 DESIGN

In the recent years, bio-inspiration has come with valuable ideas in which have brought great advances in numerous research fields. Among other, nacre has been a source of inspiration due to its exceptional mechanical performance. The outstanding toughness and strength of nacre are related to the micro-architecture of the nanocomposite, which is usually seeing as a “brick and mortar” structure (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The multiscale structure of nacre

This oriented and hierarchical organization infers a tortuous fracture path which main effect is the toughening of the material. It has been proved that layered systems consisting of two materials with very different elastic modulus lead to a crack tip shielding or anti-shielding which is translated into a change of the crack driving force and energy spent by the fracture process [2].

Figure 2: Crack path in a “Brick and mortar” structure

In this line, a bio-inspired nacre-liked design of CFRPs is explored in this work with the aim of increasing toughness, reducing delamination by crack deflection and increasing the ductile performance of CFRPs laminates. Some studies have already demonstrated that this structure increases the ductile performance and damage resistance of the composite materials [3-5].

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Manufacturing process

The novelty of this work is to manufacture bio-inspired nacre-liked CFRP laminates by creating a “brick and mortar” structure through an automated process and materials already present in the aerospace industry. Specifically, an automated tape layer machine (ATL) has been used to manufacture the bioinspired laminates from AS4/8552 prepreg.

The methodology consists of the following: the ATL head has two knives that make continuous cuts perpendicular to the fiber direction in the unidirectional prepreg roll (Figure 3A) and, at the same time, the head places the plies in the tool with the desired stacking sequence (Figure 3B). The stacking and cut design is such that the distance between cuts is constant (l) and the overlap between even and odd plies is half the distance between cuts ($l/2$) as explained in Figure 2.

Figure 3: A) Knife cut and B) automatic stacking of cut plies

Different laminates have been manufactured successfully with different “bricks lengths” (l) from 5, to 50 mm. All the laminates have been cured in autoclave following the same curing cycle.

3.2. Experimental

3.2.1. Cut characterization

Firstly, the prepreg cut during the whole manufacturing process has been observed by optical microscopy: before and after taping as well as after curing.

Secondly, in order to study the influence of the taping velocity on the cuts precision and morphology, laminates of 1 ply and 2 plies with have been produced at four different speeds, the same day. The distance between cuts (brick length, l) and cut width (gap) have been observed and measured by optical microscopy. After taking the measurements, these laminates where cured in autoclave with the corresponding curing cycle and parameters where measured again.

Finally, a study of the cuts morphology and disposition has been performed in thick cured laminates by optical microscopy. In order to do that, micrographs of 3 polished sections of several laminates have been performed. Specifically, laminates with 6, 16 and 18 plies of each configuration have been analyzed. From each polished section, distance between cuts (brick length, l) has been measured and cuts morphology has been observed.

3.2.2. Interlaminar behaviour characterization

Fracture toughness tests (Mode I) have been performed with the aim of study the crack propagation and fracture behavior of the bio-inspired composites. In this case, the cuts of the laminates tested have been done manually.

4 RESULTS

4.1. Cut characterization

The prepreg cut performed by the knives was observed in every step of the manufacturing process. No change is appreciated through the process, pressure caused by the head when taping or autoclave pressure and resin filling seem to preserve the cut length (gap) and fibers disposition as can be appreciated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Micrograph of prepreg cut A) before taping, B) after taping and.

Regarding the influence of the taping velocity, four speeds have been used for making laminates. The brick length and cut length (gap) have been measured in 4 areas of each laminate. The results indicated that there is no influence of the taping speed in none of the parameters, the brick length presents a deviation of $\pm 1,2$ mm in general terms but deviation from the theoretical values does not vary with taping speed. Regarding gap size, in all the cases is between 0,2 and 0,4 mm. As commented before, these laminates were cured and the same parameters were measured in the same areas. The gap of the cured laminates is the same than prior to curing.

Finally, micrographs of polished sections of thick cured laminates presented no porosity and parallel plies in the different laminates, despite of the brick length, indicating a successful manufacturing process (Figure 5). Regarding the brick length study of these laminates, it can be concluded that the ATL has a precision of ± 2 mm considering the cutting process with two knives, the taping and positioning of the plies in the tool and the autoclave curing.

Figure 5: Micrograph of a cured laminate section. ATL programmed position (dotted line indicate) and cuts.

4.2. Interlaminar behavior

Fracture toughness (Mode I) tests showed an increase in the energy needed by the crack to propagate when considered as area under de curve (Figure 6). The laminates showed crack deflection and tortuous paths were observed during crack propagation. As the fracture surface area increased, so did the energy needed to propagate cracks through it.

Figure 6: Force vs Displacement representative curves obtained in the Mode I tests of samples manufactured manually.

9 CONCLUSIONS

A bio-inspired nacre-like design of CFRP laminates is proposed in this study. An automated industrial methodology is optimized in order to manufacture these new systems with a “brick and mortar” structure with ATL and AS4/8552. Several studies are performed in order to characterize the process and the resulted laminates. The initial design (brick length and gap) is maintained through the manufacturing process and invariance with taping speed is demonstrated. Apart from the successful

manufacturing of different laminates with different thicknesses following this process, fracture toughness tests (Mode I) have proven the tortuous path effect that the hierarchical structures trigger. This study opens a door to investigate the possibilities of energy dissipation and crack deflection mechanisms of new bioinspired structures within the composite industry.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank L. C. Herrera-Ramírez, C. Vasquez and M. Castillo for the preliminary results of this project. We would also like to thank J. L. Jiménez, M. de la Cruz and J. Martín Muñoz for their assistance with the sample preparation.

REFERENCES

- [1] V. Dikshit, Somen K. Bhudolia and S. C. Joshi, Multiscale Polymer Composites: A Review of the Interlaminar Fracture Toughness Improvement, *Fibers* (2017), 5, 38 (doi:10.3390/fib5040038).
- [2] G. M. Luz and Joao F. Mano, Biomimetic design of materials and biomaterials inspired by the structure of nacre, *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A* (2009) 367, 1587–1605.
- [3] G. Czél, S. Pimenta, M. R. Wisnom and P. Robinson, Demonstration of pseudo-ductility in unidirectional discontinuous carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg composites. *Composites Science and Technology* (2015), 106, 110–119.
- [4] G. Bullegas, J. Benoliel, P. L. Fenelli, S. T. Pinho and S. Piment., Towards quasi isotropic laminates with engineered fracture behaviour for industrial applications, *Composites Science and Technology* (2018), 165, 290–306.
- [5] R. Malkin, M. Yasaei, R. S. Trask and I. P. Bond, Bio-inspired laminate design exhibiting pseudo-ductile (graceful) failure during flexural loading, *Composites: Part A*, 54 (2013), 107–116 (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2013.07.008>).